

opción

Revista de Antropología, Ciencias de la Comunicación y de la Información, Filosofía,
Lingüística y Semiótica, Problemas del Desarrollo, la Ciencia y la Tecnología

Año 35, 2019, Especial N°

22

Revista de Ciencias Humanas y Sociales
ISSN 1012-1537/ ISSNc: 2477-9385
Depósito Legal pp 198402ZU45

Universidad del Zulia
Facultad Experimental de Ciencias
Departamento de Ciencias Humanas
Maracaibo - Venezuela

Subjective Well-Being Of Russian Female Personnel As An Indicator Of Socio-Psychological Age

¹Irina S. Leonova, ²Liudmila N. Zakharova, ³Francisco D. Bretones

¹University of Granada, Spain

**Lobachevsky State University of Nizhny Novgorod, Nizhny Novgorod,
Russian Federation**

**²Lobachevsky State University of Nizhny Novgorod, Nizhny Novgorod,
Russian Federation**

³University of Granada, Spain

Abstract

The present work is theoretical and empirical research on the socio-psychological age of female personnel at enterprises with different organizational cultures. The main indicators of socio-psychological age include the level of commitment to organizational values, readiness for organizational changes, involvement in labor activity, and fatigue. The respondents are female employees of two large industrial enterprises. The female personnel working in a market-hierarchical type of organizational culture with an expressed innovative component reflect characteristics of a younger socio-psychological age while those working at an enterprise with a hierarchical-clan type of organizational culture display characteristics of a more senior socio-psychological age.

Keywords: chronological age, gender stereotypes, fatigue, labor involvement, organizational culture

Bienestar Subjetivo de Plantilla Femenina Como Indicador de Edad Psicológica Social

Resumen

Aquí se empuende un estudio teórico y empírico de la edad psicológica social de las empleadas de empresas de culturas organizativas diferentes. Los indicadores principales de edad psicológica social son el nivel de dedicación a valores organizativos, preparación para cambios organizativos, participación en actividades laborales y fatiga. Los encuestados incluyeron las trabajadoras de dos empresas industriales grandes. Las empleadas de empresas de la cultura organizativa hierárquica comerciable con un componente inovativo expreso reflejan las características de una edad psicológica social más temprana. Las trabajadoras de empresas de la cultura organizativa hierárquica de clan muestran las características de una edad psicológica social más madura.

Palabras clave: edad cronológica, estereotipos de género, fatiga, participación laboral, cultura organizativa

1. Introduction

In recent years, people are increasingly discussing the extension of the active working period of their lives. Various studies reveal the importance of older people's involvement in work both for maintaining personal health and positive psychological well-being, as well as for the country's economy (Johnson et al.; 2015; Kajitani, 2011; Maimaris et al., 2010; Staudinger, 2015; Wong and Shobo, 2017).

Older people, especially women, have difficulty finding employment in many countries, including Europe and the United States, yet this usually refers to people older than 65. In Russia, employment problems begin at the age of 45 (Albrecht et al., 2003; Klimenko, and Posukhova, 2017; Petrova, 2013; Staudinger, 2015). Employer decision-making is determined by a range of factors, but legal provisions also affect this process. In addition, age and gender discrimination tend to be explained in terms of persistent negative social stereotypes about old age.

Analyzing scientifically accumulated data on heterogeneous manifestations of age as a biosocial and interactive phenomenon with all its complexities allows considering the movement of people along the age trajectory – their development and aging – as a social action. Thus, a specific set of age manifestations characterize people at each stage of this trajectory in all its chronological (Staudinger et al., 2016), biological (Jylhävä et al.,

2017), psychological (Staudinger, 2015), and socio-psychological (Rose, 1972; Zakharova et al., 2018) diversity.

Socio-psychological age (SPA) is both a subjective and a social phenomenon. On the one hand, it establishes the state of health of a person based on self-perception combining physical, intellectual and social competencies, correlated with the typical characteristics of earlier or later chronological age. On the other hand, this phenomenon includes a set of characteristics based on human perceptions by other people. In the labor market, this involves representatives of the employer and colleagues (Zakharova et al., 2018).

Negative characteristics of aging include suspicion of the new due to inflexibility, stereotypes, and conservatism. This means resistance to organizational changes, an inability to learn as a result of reduced intelligence, lowered work motivation, loss of autonomy, and consequently, reluctance to take personal responsibility in the face of stress and fatigue, with frequent episodes of chronic fatigue and disease (Nelson, 2004).

Scientific studies do not confirm a total decrease in mental functions and changes in attitudes in most elderly people (Hessel et al., 2018; Kornadt, 2016; Kunze et al., 2013; Springer et al., 2011; Vo et al., 2015). Moreover, studies of motivation that typify different ages convincingly show that people from 45-47 years of age, i.e., the age at which employment problems begin in Russia, have the most laudable motivation to continue their work, and it remains pronounced until later ages. This is the motivation of self-actualization and altruism (Ryzhov, 2012).

However, social stereotypes about old age, often shared by employers, like all stereotypes, do not arise from thin air. In this connection, one is tasked with identifying the conditions and demonstrated qualities of the worker, appropriate to the age stereotypes, and searching for mechanisms that mitigate or relieve old age stereotypes.

T. Parsons' fundamental theory considers aging as a social action; it involves studying systemic determination at the levels of culture in society, the culture of social context, the personal level, and, finally, at the level of the organism in the totality of significant psychophysiological and physiological characteristics (Parsons, 1978).

Analyzing the characteristics of age stereotypes allows correlating them with the main levels of determination of aging as a social action. At the background of general cultural values typical for a given particular society, one is advised to consider the values of employees in the organizational and cultural context. Organizational culture (OC) of enterprises is a so-

cio-psychological context of labor activity. It performs the functions of external adaptation and internal integration, based on the values of organizational development shared by the majority of employees, and manifests itself in the models of organizational and labor behavior typical for these values (Cameron and Quinn, 1999; Schein, 2004). It allows assessing the compliance/discrepancy with such key characteristic of the age stereotype as the unwillingness of older employees to accept organizational changes. At the individual level of determination of aging, the main characteristic of the employee is personal involvement in the labor process; at the level of psychophysiological regulation, fatigue can be an important indicator. Fatigue is a complex process of temporary shifts in the physiological and psychological state of the employee, which has developed as the result of hard or long-term work, disease, or stress. Fatigue is a common complaint of the elderly and is a system of physiological prevention (Eldadah, 2010; Marcora et al., 2009; Schwarz et al., 2017).

Subjective well-being at the workplace can be reasonably considered an integrated indicator of SPA. As a rule, subjective well-being includes a balance of positive and negative emotions and cognitive assessment of life satisfaction (Linley et al., 2009). In this study, subjective well-being included an assessment of satisfaction with one's working life at the level of social and psychological well-being in the workforce, while positive and negative emotional components are considered as a subjective assessment of fatigue and age-related well-being.

If an employee is personally involved in a work activity, feels cheerful and does not experience chronic fatigue, is comfortable at the workplace and perceives themselves psychologically young, is ready to support progressive organizational changes and to continue working, then they are a happy productive employee (Peiró et al., 2014; Rauschenbach, 2012) and do not fall under the characteristics of age stereotypes. These characteristics are not personal, since subjective well-being requires an organizational environment that either generates, supports or hinders it. Like any personal phenomenon, social and psychological age should be studied in context (Guimond et al., 2010, Posthuma, 2009). Women are especially sensitive to conditions that support their positive age sense of self.

The peculiarity of the economic situation in modern Russia is that efficient enterprises coexist with enterprises experiencing long-term difficulties with modernization. As a rule, the organizational and cultural conditions of these enterprises differ significantly (Dyrin, 2009; Zakharova et al., 2017), and they provide the organizational context for manifesting the socio-psy-

chological age of the personnel.

2. Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in two stages. At the first stage, the analysis of available corporate documentation was conducted to identify the respective involvement in innovative processes in different enterprises; the research of OC was carried out by means of the OCAI method used by K. Cameron and R. Quinn (Marcora et al., 2009). Two large industrial enterprises were selected. The first is an enterprise having long-term problems with modernization; it gets state support, with an organizational culture of the hierarchical-clan type, typical for enterprises of the pre-reform Soviet period with an administrative-command economic model (hereafter the ordinary enterprise). The company management was changed 1.5 years ago. The fresh management corps is trying to overcome the backlog and steer the company towards an innovative path of development. The second one is a successful enterprise with high requirements for technological and managerial innovations and a market-hierarchical type of OC with a pronounced innovative component (hereafter – the innovative enterprise). Respondents. The study involved female personnel of these enterprises who had at least 3 years of experience, i.e., they were adapted to the organizational conditions of enterprises. Three age groups were selected (up to 35 years, 36-55 years, and older than 55 years), with 30 people in each group, except for the senior group of innovative enterprises (25 women). Methods. Values of female personnel in relation to the vector of organizational development were evaluated by the diagnostical method of OC used by K. Cameron and R. Quinn (OCAI) (Cameron and Quinn, 1999); labor involvement was determined by the method of personal self-identification used by Kuhn and McPartland (1954). Subjective well-being was based on the following indicators: self-assessment of fatigue from work, from organizational relationships and from homework, self-assessment of psychological age relative to chronological age, and social and psychological well-being in the workforce. For this purpose, the author developed a questionnaire which included direct scaling. In addition, 5 managers who know the personnel independently assessed the socio-psychological age of female personnel, and correlated their impressions of employee participation in the workplace and how they complied with corporate requirements; they also correlated behavioral manifestations with ideas about the chronological age. For statistical data processing, nonparametric methods for determining statistically significant differences between groups of indicators were used, along with the Spearman rank correlation method.

3. Results and Discussion

The data in Tables 1 and 2 show that the female personnel of enterprises with different types of OC have statistically significant differences in values, labor involvement and subjective well-being in labor activity.

Differences in values as predictors of behavior are fundamental. In an ordinary enterprise, regardless of age, the female personnel have in common the characteristics of commitment to the values of relations and the values of order. Moreover, the actual type of OC in this enterprise is hierarchical-clan, and the female personnel wants absolute domination of clan values that fully correspond to the pre-reform characteristics of organizational conditions, and demonstrates personnel resistance to the organizational. Such value characteristics fully correspond to the age stereotype, and they are typical of older women as well as their younger colleagues, although when hiring, these characteristics of potential young employees are usually ignored by management, and the stereotype applies only to older women. In the innovative enterprise, the value priority of organizational development of women's personnel is the market-innovative vector which consistently characterizes the current situation. The values of relations are markedly pronounced in comparison to bureaucratic values, and they are clear for women's personnel; however, they do not pose a threat to development, since they are regulated by market-innovative value priorities. Thus, in the innovative enterprise, the value priorities of the female personnel contribute to its innovative development, and the female personnel of older ages do not fall under the characteristics of age stereotypes.

Participation of female personnel members in the labor force in these enterprises also differs significantly in statistical terms. This is especially true for young women today (1.9 vs. 1.4, $p \leq 0.05$) and in the future (1.9 vs. 1.3, $p \leq 0.01$), middle-aged women being the exception. However, in the five-year perspective, middle-aged female personnel maintain their achieved level of labor involvement, while the personnel in an ordinary enterprise lose statistical significance. Female personnel of older age both in the innovative and ordinary enterprise lose in the long-term level of labor involvement, but it remains significantly higher than that of women of the same age group in the ordinary enterprise (1.8 against 1.2, $p \leq 0.05$). Thus, in terms of labor involvement, the female personnel of an ordinary enterprise are much more in line with age stereotypes than in an innovative enterprise.

The subjective well-being of female personnel in enterprises with different types of OC is of particular interest. Firstly, women of all age groups

psychologically feel better in conditions of a market-hierarchical culture which has a pronounced innovative component than in conditions of a hierarchical-clan OC. At first glance, this seems illogical, since it is traditionally believed that the value of relationship provides greater satisfaction with the work situation, and for women in an ordinary enterprise, the value of the relationship unconditionally dominates. Yet it should be noted that the enterprise is in the process of making organizational changes directed at reorganizing the existing OC. This generates discontent, tensions, and poor psychological well-being.

Second, it is noteworthy that women in an ordinary enterprise are characterized by a higher level of fatigue from organizational relations. Interestingly, it decreases from one age group to another and is minimal in older women. Apparently, older women already found effective ways of confronting and adapting to what is happening. They also get tired of work much less than their younger colleagues, although it should be noted that in an innovative enterprise fatigue results not only from organizational relationships but also from working less than in an ordinary enterprise. This is an important point, because it shows that high technology in the workplace really reduces fatigue and makes the work less onerous. Indirect confirmation of the reliability of the results is provided by the fatigue indicators of homework – it is less in all categories of respondents than fatigue from work and organizational relationships. At the same time, employees of the innovative enterprise are less tired of housework, probably because they have more energy for household chores.

Third, women of all age groups feel younger in the OC of the innovative enterprise, while young and middle-aged women in the OC of the ordinary enterprise feel older than they are. The hierarchical culture is unpleasant especially for young women; on average, they feel older by more than 7 years. Besides, in more than half of the cases, managers assess young women's socio-psychological age as older. The only age subgroup – older women – in an ordinary enterprise positions itself as on average almost 6 years younger than the chronological age. However, this can be interpreted as a specific feature of women – in older years they hide their age. Managers, however, rate most of the female personnel in the senior group (54.3%) as personnel with an older socio-psychological age. However, the labor involvement of older women in the ordinary enterprise ranks quite high – 2 points. It is statistically lower than the labor involvement of female personnel at the innovative enterprise (2.0 vs. 2.6, $p \leq 0.01$) and falls sharply in the future – up to 1.2 points against 1.8 points in the female

personnel in the innovative enterprise, who expect and wish to continue working at a later age.

Thus, older women represent the personnel group that positions itself as the most strongly involved in the labor process and, therefore, they appear not to fall under age stereotypes. Nevertheless, one must note the different nature of their involvement in the organizational culture. Women in the innovative enterprise feel young and cheerful and want to work in the market-innovative paradigm. Managers estimate more than 40% of them as younger than their chronological age and almost 35% as corresponding to it. In the ordinary enterprise, almost 55 % of the women are rated by managers as older than, and 27.5% as corresponding to, their chronological age. These results clearly show differences in psychological and socio-psychological ages. For older women in ordinary enterprises, work is now the last stage where they can demonstrate their feminine qualities while they remain in the system with the dominant value of relationship, but their labor involvement does not support the enterprise's movement to a new level of development.

Analysis of correlations between organizational values and cultural preferences indicators and subjective well-being indicators of female personnel yields additional opportunities for understanding the specific manifestations of SPA female personnel (Tables 3-4).

The first and the main finding is that in the innovative enterprise, no significant correlations with the chronological age of the respondents are demonstrated, while such connections are found among the female personnel of the innovative enterprise with the market-hierarchical type of OC with a pronounced innovative component. The older the chronological age, the younger the female employees in an ordinary enterprise position themselves. In an innovative enterprise, women simply feel younger and less tired, regardless of their chronological age. This indicates that the OC in an ordinary enterprise is close to the socio-cultural characteristics of society, while the OC in an innovative enterprise is built on other principles: success in the external competitive environment, internal competition, evaluation of human performance and quality of his or her work.

The next important point is that in an ordinary enterprise, there is an inverse connection between fatigue in organizational relationships and chronological age. This indicates that female personnel, and the chronological age, are becoming increasingly indifferent to corporate requirements, which, along with the dominance of the value of relationships and low involvement in the labor process, reduces the value of such personnel.

This is reflected in the managers' negative assessment of the SPA in female personnel. They see psychologically old people, and it confirms their commitment to age stereotypes.

Separate significant correlations allow detailing the obtained data. This is especially important with regard to the heterogeneity of the personnel in enterprises. Thus, at the ordinary enterprise one can allocate significant positive correlations between the involvement of female personnel in the labor process and accepting the vector of the market and innovative development as defined by management. This implies that management has supporters who need to be sought in the environment of people who are truly involved in the work process and who see for themselves certain professional and work prospects in the future. These are more psychologically young women ($r=.469$): the psychologically older the employees, the less inclined they are to accept innovative values. Besides, the introduction of market principles causes fatigue in organizational relationships ($r=.337$). The psychologically younger the employees, the more involved they are in labor activity ($r= -.429$), and the older the employees, the more they tend to bureaucratic relations ($r=.327$).

The link of psychological age and bureaucratic and innovative values is traced also in the innovative enterprise, ($r=.360$) and ($r=-.512$) respectively: the older the employees, the less they accept innovative values and are more inclined to accept bureaucratic values. In the innovative enterprise, there is a direct link between fatigue and organizational relations; if bureaucracy increases ($r=.381$), there is an inverse connection between its strengthening and the market component ($r=-.368$).

4. Conclusions

(1) Organizational culture is an important social regulator of gender manifestations given the social and psychological ages of the personnel. Female personnel within one OC are characterized by common features but with some specific differences.

(2) Subjective well-being of the personnel can be considered as indicating the SPA of the personnel.

(3) Female personnel of enterprises with a hierarchical-clan OC are typical, and regardless of the chronological age, have the characteristics of the older SPA, in comparison to the female personnel of an innovative enterprise with the OC of a market-hierarchical type with an expressed innovative component.

(4) Certain heterogeneity of women's personnel in an ordinary enterprise, relative to the SPA, opens the door for management which is im-

plementing market-innovative organizational changes, the possibility of selecting mentors and a pool of new employees with a younger socio-psychological age. They provide significant links in succession with their willingness to work in a new management paradigm.

The authors are grateful to the University of Oslo and its Representative Office in St. Petersburg – The Norwegian University Center of St Petersburg (Russia) for the initiation of studies of social psychology of age and aging, and also for the opportunity of initial approbation of the results at the interdisciplinary seminar ‘Dimensions of Ageing’ organized in 2018.

Acknowledgement

The reported study was funded by RFBR as research project No. 19-013-00910. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- ALBRECHT, G. L., FITZPATRICK, R., and SCRIMSHAW, S. C. (eds.). 2003. *The Handbook of Social Studies in Health and Medicine*. SAGE Publications, Thousand Oaks. California (USA).
- CAMERON, K. S. and QUINN, R. E. 1999. *Diagnosing and Changing Organizational Culture*. Jossey-Bass, A Wiley imprint. San Francisco, CA (USA).
- DYRIN, S. P. 2009. Multivariate organizational culture of modern Russian enterprises. *Corporate culture management*. N° 1: 4 – 14.
- ELDADAH, B. A. 2010. Fatigue and fatigability in older adults. *PM&R*. N° 2: 406-413.
- GUIMOND, S., CHATARD, A., and KANG, P. 2010. Personality, social and self-categorization. *European Journal of Personality*. N° 24: 488–492.
- HESSEL, P., KINGE, J. M., SKIRBEKK, V., and STAUDINGER, U. M. 2018. Trends and determinants of the Flynn effect in cognitive functioning among older individuals in 10 European countries. *Epidemiol Community Health*. N° 72: 383–389.
- JOHNSON, J. K., SARKISIAN, N., and WILLIAMSON, J. B. 2015. Using a micro-level model to generate a macro-level model of productive successful aging. *The Gerontologist*. N° 55: 107-198.
- JYLHÄVÄ, J., PEDERSEN, N. L., and HÄGG, S. 2017. Biological age predictors. *E. BioMedicine*. N° 2: 9-36.
- KAJITANI, S. 2011. Working in old age and health outcomes in Japan. *Japan and the World Economy*. N° 23: 153-162.
- KLIMENKO, L. V. and POSUKHOVA, O. Y. 2017. Gender aspects of precarization of labor in Russian society. *Woman in Russian Society*. N° 1: 29-40.

- KORNADT A. E. 2016. Do age stereotypes as social role expectations for older adults influence personality development? *Journal of Research in Personality*. N° 60: 51-55.
- KUHN, M. H. and MCPARTLAND, T. S. 1954. An Empirical Investigation of Self-Attitudes. *American Sociological Review*. N° 19: 68-76.
- KUNZE, F., BOEHM, S., and BRUCH, H. 2013. Age, resistance to change, and job performance. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*. N° 28: 741-760.
- LINLEY, P. A. MALTBY, J. WOOD, A. M. OSBORNE, G., and HURLING, R. 2009. Measuring happiness: The higher order factor structure of subjective and psychological well-being measures. *Personality and Individual Differences*. N° 47: 878-884.
- MAIMARIS W., HOGAN H., and LOCK K. 2010. The impact of working beyond traditional retirement ages on mental health: Implications for public health and welfare policy. *PHR*. N° 31: 532-548.
- MARCORA, S. M., STAIANO, W., and MANNING, V. 2009. Mental fatigue impairs physical performance in humans. *European Journal of Applied Physiology*. N° 106: 857-864.
- NELSON, T. D. (ed.). 2004. *Ageism. Stereotyping and prejudice against older persons*. MIT Press. Cambridge, MA (USA).
- PARSONS, T. 1978. *Action Theory and the Human Condition*. Free Press. New York (USA).
- PEIRÓ, J. M., AYALA, Y., TORDERA, N., LORENTE, L., and RODRÍGUEZ, I. 2014. Sustainable well-being at work: a review and reformulation. *Papeles del Psicólogo*. N° 35: 5-14.
- PETROVA, Zh. V. 2013. Discriminatory practices towards the retired by age in the professional and labor sphere as a problem of the socio-economic policy of the state: gender aspect. *Woman in Russian Society*. N° 4: 23-32.
- POSTHUMA, R. A. 2009. Age stereotypes in the workplace: common stereotypes, moderators, and future research directions. *Journal of Management*. N° 35: 158-188.
- RAUSCHENBACH, C., GÖRITZ, A. S., and HERTEL, C. 2012. Age stereotypes about emotional resilience at work. *Educational Gerontology*. N° 38: 511-519.
- ROSE, C. L. 1972. The measurement of social age. *The International Journal of Aging and Human Development*. N° 3: 153-168.
- RYZHOV, B. N. 2012. Systems periodization of the development. *Systems Psychology and Sociology*. N° 5.
- SCHEIN, E. H. 2004. *Organizational Culture and Leadership*. Jossey-Bass,

A Wiley Imprint. San Francisco, CA (USA).

SCHWARZ, J. F. A., AKERSTEDT, T., LINDBERG, E., GRUBER, G., FISCHER, H., and THEORELL-HAGLOW, J. 2017. Age affects sleep microstructure more than sleep macrostructure. *The Journal of Sleep Research*. N° 26: 277-287.

SPRINGER, K. W., PUDROVSKA, T., and HAUSER, R. M. 2011. Does psychological well-being change with age? Longitudinal tests of age variations and further exploration of the multidimensionality of Ryff's model of psychological well-being. *Open journal social science research*. N° 40: 392-398.

STAUDINGER, U. M. 2015. Images of aging: Outside and inside perspectives. *Annual Review of Gerontology and Geriatrics*. N° 35 (1): 187-210.

STAUDINGER, U. M., FINKELSTEIN, R., CALVO, E., and SIVARAMAKRISHNAN, K. A. 2016. Global view on the effects of work on health in later life. *The Gerontologist*. N° 56: 281-292.

VO, K., FORDER, P. M., TAVENER, M., RODGERS, B., BANKS, E., BAUMAN, A., and BYLES, J. B. 2015. Retirement, age, gender and mental health: findings from the 45 and up Study. *Aging and Mental Health*. N° 19: 647-657.

WONG, J. D. and SHOBO, Y. 2017. The moderating influences of retirement transition, age, and gender on daily stressors and psychological distress. *The International Journal of Aging and Human Development*. N° 85: 90-107.

ZAKHAROVA, L., LEONOVA, I., and KOROBAYNIKOVA, E. 2017. Value Conflict and Psychological Resilience of Personnel of Russian Enterprises. UNN. Nizhny Novgorod (Russia).

ZAKHAROVA, L., LEONOVA, I., and MARTIANOVA, T. 2018. Gender manifestations of socio-psychological age of the personnel in companies with organizational culture of different types. *The International Journal Theoretical and Practical Aspects of Management*. N° 7: 107-117.

Table 1. Organizational and cultural preferences and indicators of subjective well-being of female personnel in organizational cultures of different types

Subgroups	Ent	OC-preferences										EM (%)				
		C	A	M	H	A	P	W	SE	W	F	F	SP	younger	older	chronological
Y: up to 35	O	37.	12.	18.	32.	1,	1,	-	7,3	6.	8.3	4.	-1,4	32,9	51,	15.3
	R	2	4	3	1	4	3	-	-	5.	1	4	-1,4	32,9	8	15.3
	IN	27.	25.	30.	16.	1,	1,	-	-	5.	4.2	3.	2.8	52.5	12.	35.0
M: 36 - 54	O	41.	12.	15.	30.	1,	1,	T	4,7	8.	6,7	5.	-4.1	35,4	52,	12.5
	R	5	6	7	3	3	1	T	4,7	0	8.	9	-4.1	35,4	1	12.5
	IN	21.	27.	35.	15.	1,	1,	-	-	5.	4.8	4.	3.8	43.3	22.	34.5
O: 55 and older	O	40.	14.	16.	28.	2,	1,	*	-	4.	5.2	4.	-2.2	18.2	54.	27.5
	R	4	6	3	8	0	2	*	5.9	8	8	8	-2.2	18.2	3	27.5
	IN	21.	28.	34.	15.	2,	1,	*	-	4.	4.0	4.	4.0	42.9	22.	34.5
		8	3	2	7	6	8		6.2	7	6	6	4.0	42.9	6	34.5

Ent – type of enterprise; C - clan, A- adhocratic, M - market. H - hierarchical elements in the organizational preferences of female personnel; Ac- present labor involvement, P- labor involvement in a five-year perspective; SEA - age self-esteem, WF – work fatigue, FOI – fatigue from organizational interaction, FHW – fatigue from homework, JS – job satisfaction; EM – evaluation of managers, OR – ordinary, IN- innovative enterprises; Y – sub-group of young, M- middle, O – older age; W – the Wilcoxon test, * - $p \leq 0.05$; ** - $p \leq 0.01$, T – tendency; - – no statistically significant differences.

Table 2. The statistical significance of the differences between the indicators characterizing the socio-psychological age of female personnel of enterprises with different types of organizational culture (Mann–Whitney U-test)

Subgroups	C	A	M	H	Ac	P	SEA	WF	FOI	FHW	SPW
Y: OR-IN	*	**	**	**	*	**	*	-	**	-	*
M: OR-IN	**	**	**	**	-	*	*	*	-	*	*
O: OR-IN	**	**	**	*	**	*	-	-	*	-	*
OR: Y-M	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	**	**	-	**
OR: M-O	-	-	-	-	-	-	**	**	-	-	-
OR: Y-O	-	-	-	-	-	-	**	-	**	-	-
IN: Y-M	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
IN: M-O	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
IN: Y-O	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Ent – type of enterprise; C - clan, A- adhocratic, M - market. H - hierarchical elements in the organizational preferences of female personnel; Ac-present labor involvement, P- labor involvement in a five-year perspective; SEA - age self-esteem, WF – work fatigue, FOI – fatigue from organizational interaction, FHW – fatigue from homework, JS – job satisfaction; EM – evaluation of managers, OR – ordinary, IN- innovative enterprises; Y – sub-group of young, M- middle, O – older age; W – the Wilcoxon test, * - $p \leq 0.05$; ** - $p \leq 0.01$, T – tendency; - – no statistically significant differences.

Table 3. Correlations between chronological age, organizational development values, labor involvement and subjective well-being of female personnel in the organizational culture of the hierarchical-clan type

Indicators	1-chron	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
2 - C	,150										
Organizational and cultural preferences 3 - A	,191	-	,652*								
4 - M	-,179	-	,592*	,555*							
5 - B	-,148	-	,440*	-,175	-,283						
6 - Ac	-,138	-	,462*	,596*	,394*	-,119					
Self-identification 7 - P	-,023	-	,500*	,468*	,251	,104	,512*				
8 - SEA	-,526*	-,040	-,469*	-,105	,327*	-	-	-,429*	,212		
9 - WF	-,245	,180	-,219	-,122	,084	-,260	-	,172	,335*		
Subjective well-being 10 - FOI	-,496*	-,280	,177	,337*	,053	,128	,064	,222	,138		
11 - FHW	,086	-,117	,098	,100	,099	,129	-,041	-,055	,283	,164	
12 - SPW	-,115	-,148	,164	,318*	-,261	,220	,032	-,069	-	,097	,037

12 - SPW -,115 -,148 ,164 ,318* -,261 ,220
 ,032 -,069 -,268 ,097 ,037

chron – chronological age, C - clan, A- adhocratic, M - market, B - hierarchical components of organizational culture; Self-identification: Ac – currently, P – the five-year perspective; SEA - age self-esteem, WF – work fatigue; FOI – fatigue from organizational interaction; FHW – fatigue from homework; SPW - social and psychological well-being; * -p ≤ 0.05 (Spearman’s Rank Correlation coefficient).

Table 4. Correlations between chronological age, organizational develop-

ment values, labor involvement and subjective well-being of female personnel in the organizational culture of the market-hierarchical type, with a strong innovation component

Indicators	1- chron	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
2 - C	-,241										
Organizational and cultural preferences	3 - A	,288	-								
	4 - M	,115	-,757*	-,303*							
	5 - B	-,145	,370*	-	-						
				,650*	,565*						
Self- identification	6 - Ac	-,019	,178	-,073	-,259	,067					
	7 - P	-,268	,173	-,184	-,207	,177	,733*				
	8 - SEA	-,246	,329*	-	-	,360*	,135	,125			
				,512*	,315*						
	9 - WF	-,199	,260	-,268	-,271	,340*	,218	,115	,304*		
Subjective well-being	10 - FOI	-,050	,311*	-,271	-	,381*	,148	,101	,194	,645*	
					,368*						
	11 - FHW	,009	,220	-,246	-,116	,153	,256	,255	,168	,376*	,499*
	12 - SPW	,095	-,145	,085	,165	-,222	,020	-	-,086	-,245	,017
								,070			,137

chron – chronological age, C - clan, A- adhocratic, M - market, B - hierarchical components of organizational culture; Self-identification: Ac – currently, P – the five-year perspective; SEA - age self-esteem, WF – work fatigue; FOI – fatigue from organizational interaction; FHW – fatigue from homework; SPW - social and psychological well-being; * - $p \leq 0.05$ (Spearman's Rank Correlation coefficient).

**UNIVERSIDAD
DEL ZULIA**

opción

Revista de Ciencias Humanas y Sociales

Año 35, Especial No. 22 (2019)

Esta revista fue editada en formato digital por el personal de la Oficina de Publicaciones Científicas de la Facultad Experimental de Ciencias, Universidad del Zulia.

Maracaibo - Venezuela

www.luz.edu.ve

www.serbi.luz.edu.ve

produccioncientifica.luz.edu.ve